

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№ 10

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

IQTISODIYOT&TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Elektron nashr. 1240 sahifa.

2025-yil, 22-oktyabr

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate

Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society

Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences

Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor

Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor

Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor

Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)

Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)

Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan

Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan

Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences

Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer

Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor

Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)

Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)

Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow))

Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE

Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI

Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Geografiya fanlari doktori, professori
Umirzoqov Ja'sur Artiqboy o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Zebo Kuldasheva, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilkhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Khusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Rakhimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor
Umirzokov Jasur Artiqboy ugli, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor
Zebo Kuldasheva, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

QAYTA TIKLANUVCHI YASHIL ENERGIYA: BARCHA UCHUN MUHIM MASALA.....	13
Muxiddin Kalonov	
MOLIYAVIY INNOVATSIYALAR: IQTISODIY MOHIYATI, QO‘LLANILISHI VA RIVOJLANISHI.....	19
Quliyev Begimqul Melikovich	
SAVDO KORXONALARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA STATISTIK TAHLIL USULLARIDAN FOYDALANISHNING AHAMIYATI.....	24
Sabirova Oysuluv Shonazarovna	
KORXONANING MEBEL MAXSULOTLARI BOZORIDAGI O‘RNINI KENGAYTIRISH USULLARI	30
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	
IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA INVESTITSIYA KO‘RSATKICHLARI TIZIMINING FUNKSIONAL JIHATI.....	35
Alabayev Sobitxon	
MAMLAKATIMIZDA MAHSULOTLARNING MUVOFIQLIGINI BAHOLASH AMALIYOTI.....	40
Zakirov Ansabxon Akaidinovich	
ПЕСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ЗЕЛЁНЫХ ОБЛИГАЦИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	48
Саидахмедова Аида Мирзаевна	
KORXONALAR FAOLIYATIDA DEBITOR VA KREDITOR QARZDORLIKNI BOSHQARISH	55
Mirzayev Ozod Furkatovich	
AHOLI PUL DAROMADLARI VA HUDUDIY IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISH KO‘RSATKICHLARI O‘RTASIDAGI EKONOMETRIK TAHLIL.....	59
Qodirov Farrux Ergash o‘g‘li	
BUDJET RESURSLARI SHAKLLANISHIDA HUDUDNING SOLIQ SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISH VA MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIK.....	64
Yuldashev Adhamjon Axadjonovich	
SANOAT KORXONALARI IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHI TUSHUNCHASIGA NAZARIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	69
Muydinov Xusniddin Nuriddin o‘g‘li	
МЕТОДИКА УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ФИНАНСОВЫМИ ПОТОКАМИ В СИСТЕМЕ УПРАВЛЕНЧЕСКОГО УЧЕТА	73
Минутдинова Лилия Тагировна, Машарипов Озод Алимович	
ГАРМОНИЗАЦИЯ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ СТАНДАРТОВ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЕТА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН В СООТВЕТСТВИИ С МСФО	78
Абдужалилова Дилноз Абдусаттаровна	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR YORDAMIDA SMART TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING DOLZARBLIGI	84
Sobirjonov Muxiddin Toxirjon o‘g‘li	
TO‘LOVGA QOBILIYATSIZLIK HOLATIDAGI KORXONALARDA TUGATISH BALANSINI TUZISH.....	90
Nabiyev Gofurjon Nosirjon o‘g‘li	
O‘ZBEKISTON SANOATINING “YASHIL” IQTISODIYOTGA O‘TAYOTGANLIGI: IMKONIYATLAR VA CHEKLOVLAR	96
Habibullayev Oybek Asliddin o‘g‘li	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT KONTSEPTSIYASINING EVOLYUTSIYASI VA ILMIY-NAZARIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	102
Allayarov Suxrob Rustamovich	
O‘ZBEKISTONDA TO‘G‘RIDAN-TO‘G‘RI CHET EL INVESTITSIYALARINING MILLIY IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDAGI ROLI	107
Raxmatov Adxam Itolmasovich, Boynazarova Matluba Xatamovna	

HUDUDIY IJTIMOY TENGLIK VA KAMBAG'ALLIKNI YUMSHATISHDA MEHNAT RESURSLARI OMILLARI.....	114
Durumov Temur G'olibovich	
TRANSPORT TARMOG'I VA MILLIY IQTISODIYOTNING ASOSIY TARMOQLARI O'RTASIDAGI BOG'LIQLIKNI MODELASHTIRISH (SURXANDARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	121
Turayev Baxtiyor Ergashevich, Aymatov Sirojiddin To'raqul o'g'li	
РОЛЬ ЭНЕРГЕТИКИ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РОСТА ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	134
Нигматуллаева Гулчехра Нуруллаевна	
O'ZBEKISTONDA OLIY TA'LIM BOZORINING RIVOJLANISH TENDENTSIYALARI VA UNDA SIFAT MENEJMENTINING ROLI.....	139
Yuldashev Iskandar Bahromovich	
YER QA'RIDAN FOYDALANUVCHILARGA SOLIQ SOLISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	145
Zoxidov Ismatjon Yunusjon o'g'li	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA TURIZM INDUSTRIYASIDA INNOVATSION BIZNES-MODELLAR.....	151
Shaxinabonu Choriyeva	
AVTOTRANSPORT – EKSPEDITSIYA XIZMATLARI BOZORIDA MARKETING KONTSEPSIYASI.....	157
Ergasheva Mukhabbat Abdusamatovna	
“YASHIL” ENERGIYA ISHLAB CHIQRUVCHI KICHIK TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARINI SOLIQQA TORTISHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI	163
Toshtemirov To'liqin Toirjonovich	
DAVLAT IQTISODIY BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA SIYOSIY INSTITUTLARNING ROLI VA UNI KUCHAYTIRISH MEKANIZMLARI.....	166
O. Nurmuradov	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA RAQAMLI BANK TEXNOLOGIYALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ASOSLARI	171
Meyliqulov Shaxboz Xolmamat o'g'li	
СВЯЗНОСТЬ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ И РЕГИОНАЛЬНЫХ СТРАТЕГИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ: ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ.....	176
Ташматов Гайрат Ровшанович, Содиков Авазбек Мадаминович	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON RESPUBLIKASI TURIZM SOHASINI RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA RIVOJLANTIRISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	183
Zarikeyeva Miyasar Maratovna	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNING RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYASI.....	187
Saidrahmatova Zuhraxon Saidazim qizi	
O'ZBEKISTON KONCHILIK SANOATI KORXONALARIDA INVESTITSION JARAYONLARNI BOSHQARISH VA INNOVATSION XAVFLARNI KAMAYTIRISH STRATEGIYALARI	192
Kurbanova Mehriniso Nematjanovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA QULAY INVESTITSIYA MUHITINI SHAKLLANTIRISH MUAMMOLARI.....	196
Xuramov Zafar Rajabaliyevich	
PAHTA-TO'QIMACHILIK KLASTERLARIDA XOMASHYO TA'MINOTI BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASHNING XORIJ DAVLATLAR TAJRIBASI.....	201
Zakirov Abduazim Abdurashidovich	
НОВЫЙ ЭТАП ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ РЫНОЧНЫХ МЕХАНИЗМОВ В ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ.....	206
Махкамов Ибраим	
O'ZBEKISTONDA SUG'URTA BOZORINING RIVOJLANISH TENDENTSIYALARI.....	213
Xushmuradov Oman, Ismoilov Sherzod Ismoil o'g'li	
GLOBALIZATSIYA SHAROITIDA MILLIY IQTISODIYOT NAZARIYASI.....	217
Mo'ydinov Xurshidbek Abdullayevich	
DORIVOR O'SIMLIKLARNI QAYTA ISHLASHNING HOZIRGI HOLATI VA MUAMMOLARI	221
Usmonov Mirg'ulom Xoshim o'g'li	

BARQAROR IQTISODIY O‘SISHGA YERISHISHDA SUN‘IY INTELLEKT TIZIMLARINI QO‘LLASH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILASHTIRISH (XORIJIY DAVLATLAR TAJRIBASI MISOLIDA)	227
Nasrulloev Hayotjon Xabibulloevich	
НЕЙРОИНТУИТИВНЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ И ЕГО РОЛЬ В УПРАВЛЕНИИ РИСКАМИ В БИЗНЕСЕ.....	233
Ягудин Дмитрий Рустамович	
RESURLARNI SOLIQQA TORTISH AMALIYOTINING XORIJIY MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBASI VA ULARNING MILLIY SOLIQQA TIZIMIDA QO‘LLASH MASALALARI	240
Nasimdjanoov Yunusjon Zoxidovich	
O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA KICHIK TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARI UCHUN QO‘LLANILAYOTGAN SOLIQQA TORTISH MEKANIZMLARI	246
Akbarov Akramjon Ibragimzhonovich	
TO‘QIMACHILIK SANOATI KORXONALARIDA “YASHIL” MARKETINGNI JORIY ETISHNING DOLZARB JIHATLARI	250
Bazarova Fayyoza Tuxtamurodovna	
INSON KAPITALI VA IQTISODIYOTNING RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYASI.....	255
Muzaffar Raximov	
UY-JOY KOMMUNAL XO‘JALIGINI INNOVATSION RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI.....	259
Odamboyev Oybek Ravshanbek o‘g‘li	
INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS’ APPROACHES TO ATTRACTING INVESTMENT IN HUMAN CAPITAL	268
Akhmadaliyeva Nikholakhon	
RAQAMLI PLATFORMALAR ORQALI KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO‘LLARI.....	273
Vohobov Hikmatillo Ma‘mirjon o‘g‘li	
ФОРСАЙТ И ЭКОНОМИЧНЫЕ ИННОВАЦИИ КАК ДРАЙВЕРЫ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ТОРГОВЛИ САМАРКАНДА	280
Tohirova Gullola Mirkamolovna	
KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIKNI BOSHQARISHDA KASB-HUNAR TA‘LIMI BITIRUVCHILARINING O‘RNI	287
Toshpulatov Sherzod Xaydarkulovich	
DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN ECOTOURISM: INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES FOR ADVANCING GREEN TOURISM.....	292
Barno Erkayeva	
AGROTURIZM SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	296
Baymuradova Iroda Shermamatovna, Mardonova Zarifa Numonjonovna	
DAVLAT BUDJET NAZORATI TIZIMINI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO‘NALISHLARI	301
B.Sh.Mirzayev	
YOSHLAR BANDLIGIDA KO‘NIKMALAR NOMUTANOSIBLIGI MUAMMOLARI VA YECHIMLARI.....	307
Rahmatxo‘jayev Axrorxo‘ja Akmal o‘g‘li	
TO‘QIMACHILIK MAHSULOTLARINING EKSPORT SALOHİYATINI TAHLIL QILISH VA RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARINI BAHOLASH.....	311
Oqboyev Alisher Rasuljanovich	
РЕИНЖИНИРИНГ БИЗНЕС-ПРОЦЕССОВ И ИХ РОЛЬ В РАЗВИТИИ БАНКОВСКОГО БИЗНЕСА.....	317
Рахимходжаева Нодира Саидахраловна	
QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGI TA‘MINOT ZANJIRI JARAYONLARINING HOZIRGI HOLATINI TAHLIL QILISH.....	323
Ermonov Farrux	
O‘ZBEKISTONDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNI SHAKILLANTIRISH JARAYONIDA MOLIYAVIY NAZORATNI INNOVATSION TA‘LIM YO‘NALISHLARINI YO‘LGA QO‘YISH ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO‘LLARI.....	329
Turg‘unov Bahtiyor Nuriddinovich	

MARKAZIY OSIYODA SUV RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISH VA HAMKORLIKNING DOLZARB MASALALARI	334
Amanbaev Amanali Orazbaevich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA YANGI TURDAGI LOGISTIKA XIZMATLARINING USLUBIY ASOSLARI.....	338
Z. Teshayev	
O'ZBEKISTON AXBOROT-KOMMUNIKATSIYA XIZMATLARI SOHASINING AMALDAGI HOLATINI TAHLIL QILISH.....	343
Suyunov Asror Baxtiyorovich	
KORPORATIV BOSHQARUVDA LEADERSHIP 4.0 TAMOYILLARINI JORIY ETISH SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	349
Ismailov Allayor Rashidovich	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA AHOLI BANDLIGINI TA'MINLASH MASALALARI.....	355
Yusupov Farxod Adamboyevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI O'RNI VA UNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNI USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI	359
Abdullaeva Nilufar Javdat qizi	
MINTAQADA SANOAT KORXONALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING SOLISHTIRMA EKONOMETRIK MODELLARI (SURXONDARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	363
Saatmurotov Shohrux Zafar o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON SUG'URTA BOZORI: RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI VA ISTIQBOLLI IMKONIYATLAR	369
Abdurazaqov Jasur Abdunasimovich	
RAQAMLI PLATFORMALAR YORDAMIDA NORASMIY VA YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOTNI QISQARTIRISHNING QO'SHIMCHA IMKONIYATLARI TO'G'RSIDA.....	374
Nasrullayev Hikmatullo Habibulloyevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA KICHIK VA O'RTA BIZNESNI QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH MAQSADIDA "XIZMATLAR IPOTEKASI" MOLIYAVIY INSTRUMENTLARINI AMALIYOTGA JORIY QILISH MASALALARI	379
Uskenbayeva Dilnoza Boxodir qizi	
ЭКОНОМИКО-СТАТИСТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ КАПЕЛЬНОГО ОРОШЕНИЯ ПРИ ВОЗДЕЛЫВАНИИ ЛУКА В ДЖИЗАКСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ.....	384
Суюнов Шохзодбек Мурод угли	
XORIJIIY DAVLATLAR SANOAT IQTISODIYOTIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH TAJRIBASI (YAPONIYA, KOREYA VA GERMANIYA MISOLIDA)	389
Mansurova Sayyora Baxtiyor Kizi	
KORXONALARDA ISHLAB CHIQRARISH XARAJATLARI HISOBGA OLIHDA XORIY TAJRIBASINI QO'LLASH	395
Raxmatov Baxriddin Baxtiyor o'g'li	
PECULIARITIES OF THE IRRIGATION WATER DELIVERY PAYMENT IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN	399
Muminov Sherzod Kholmiraevich	
DIGITALIZATION OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS FOR EXPORT	404
Azimov R.B.	
AHOLI JON BOSHIGA UMUMIY DAROMADLAR HAJMINI TREND MODELLAR ASOSIDA PROGNOZLASH	409
Xolto'rayev Islom Ilhomovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA YANGI BANDLIK SHAKLLARI	416
Sayipov Begzod Rahimovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING YANGI DAVR SHAROITIDA MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI BAHOLASH USULLARI VA INDIKATORLARI	422
Sadikov Iskandar Gayratovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARI AKTIVLARINING SAMARADORLIGINI IQTISODIY-STATISTIK TAHLILI	427
Ibrohimov Davronbek Muhammadi o'g'li	

MAHALLIY BUDJET SOLIQLI DAROMADLARI BAZASI BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA SOLIQLAR TA'SIRCHANLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI	433
<i>Isoqov Zafarjon Zokirjonovich</i>	
TOSHKENT SHAHRIDAGI YIRIK SOLIQ TO'LOVCHILARNING SOLIQ QARZDORLIGI TAHLILI	438
<i>Soipov Boburmirzo Nosirjon o'g'li</i>	
РОЛЬ ЖИЛИЩНОЙ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРЫ В СИСТЕМЕ КОМПЛЕКСНОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ТЕРРИТОРИЙ МЕЗОУРОВНЯ.....	446
<i>Далиев Ахтам Шарафудинович</i>	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOAT KORXONALARIDA INSON RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISHDA XORIJ TAJRIBALARINING ZARURLIGI.....	454
<i>Abdullayev Dostonbek G'ofurjon o'g'li</i>	
TURISTIK KLASTERLARNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA ULARNING HUDUDIY IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHDAGI O'RNI.....	458
<i>Xaitov Oxunjon Nomoz o'g'li</i>	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARIDA RESURS TA'MINOTI BOSHQARUVINING NAZARIY KONSEPSIYALARI VA MODELLARI.....	462
<i>Arziqulova Oybar chin Eshquvat qizi</i>	
XIZMATLAR SEKTORIDA RAQAMLI INNOVATSIYALAR VA MIJOZLAR EHTIYOJLARINI QONDIRISH MEKANIZMLARI.....	467
<i>Xudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich</i>	
СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКАЯ СУЩНОСТЬ ПОДГОТОВКИ КАДРОВ В РАЗВИТИИ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА.....	472
<i>Базаров Бердымурад Улугмуродович, Атавуллаева Саида Джумабекмуродовна</i>	
TURIZM SOHASIDA KADRLAR SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISHNING TASHKILIY-IQTISODIY MEKANIZMI.....	478
<i>Ho'jaqulov Bobur Rustam o'g'li</i>	
KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA DAVLATNING RO'LI	483
<i>Nabiyeva Muxabbat Djabirxanovna</i>	
"HOW GREEN INVESETMENTS CAN EFFECT ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES"	485
<i>Farangiz Ma'rufjonovna Pirmatova</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA UZOQ MUDDATLI RESURSLAR MANBALARI VA ULARNING HAJMINI OSHIRISHNING ZARURIYATI.....	493
<i>Abduraxmonov Akmal Nurmamat o'g'li</i>	
GLOBAL BOSHQARUV VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHDA YASHIL TEXNOLOGIYALARNING ROLI	498
<i>M.Sh. Tolipov</i>	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕХАНИЗМОВ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ ФИНАНСОВОЙ УСТОЙЧИВОСТИ ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКИХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ	504
<i>Буранбаева Шоира Рустамовна</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA PIYOZ YETISHTIRISHDA TOMCHILATIB SUG'ORISHNI QO'LLASH ISTIQBOLLARI	508
<i>Suyunov Shohzodbek Murod o'g'li</i>	
YENGIL SANOAT KORXONALARINING RIVOJLANISHIGA BOSHQARUV MADANIYATIDAN FOYDALANISHNING TA'SIRI.....	513
<i>Aknazarova Zebiniso Bagdadovna</i>	
ISHLAB CHIQRISHNI DIVERSIFIKATSIYALASH SHAROITIDA KORPORATIV BOSHQARUVNING TASHKILIY-IQTISODIY MEKANIZM SAMARADORLIGINI ANIQLASH USULLARI	518
<i>Qurbaniyazov Shaxzodbek Karimovich</i>	
KICHIK BIZNESNI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA JOYLASHTIRISHNING IQTISODIY VA TASHKILIY ASOSLARI	524
<i>Salimov Burxon Abubakirovich</i>	
"YASHIL" IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA UNDA ENERGIYADAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	530
<i>Berdiyeva Aziza G'anisher qizi</i>	

SIRKULAR IQTISODIYOTDAN KORXONA VA TADBIRKORLAR MANFAATLARI	535
Sodikov Zokir Rustamovich	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK SOHASIDA ME'YORIY-HUQUQIY BAZANI ISHLAB CHIQISH.....	541
Xolmirzayev Ulug'bek Abdulazizovich, Ubaydullayev Toxirjon Abdullajanovich	
MINTAQA OZIQ-OVQAT MAHSULOTLARI CHAKANA SAVDOSIDA SHADOW WAREHOUSE MODELIGA ASOSLANGAN YETKAZIB BERISH TIZIMINI JORIY QILISH.....	548
Ibrayimova Dilnoza Abdisherpovna	
XIZMATLAR SAVDOSI SOHASIDA O'ZBEKISTONNING XALQARO HAMKORLIK IMKONIYATLARI	555
Qodirjonov A.M.	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATINI IQTISODIY RIVOJLANTIRISHDA RESURLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH KONSEPSIYASINI SHAKLLANTIRISH USLUBIYOTI.....	559
Madraximova Gulasal Ro'zimboy qizi	
ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЕ ТРЕНДЫ СМАРТ-ТУРИЗМА И ИХ ПРИМЕНИМОСТЬ К КУЛЬТУРНОМУ НАСЛЕДИЮ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	564
Салихбаев Нурсултон Равшанович	
IJTIMOIIY NIHOYA TIZIMI VA IJTIMOIIY TIBBIY XIZMATLAR O'ZARO BOG'LIQLIGINING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	572
Shanazarov Farrux Shodiyorovich	
ТЕХНИКО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЕ ОБОСНОВАНИЕ РАЗРАБОТКИ МОБИЛЬНОГО ПРИЛОЖЕНИЯ JOB VARAKA ДЛЯ РЫНКА ТРУДА УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	577
Еримбетова Улбосын Маратовна	
TASHQI SAVDO VA INVESTITSIYALAR TAHLILI HAMDA ULARNING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKKA TA'SIRI.....	582
Jalolov Bekzod Sherzod o'g'li	
“O'ZBEKISTONDA KICHIK VA O'RTA BIZNESLAR UCHUN SUN'IY INTELLEKT ASOSIDA MOLIYAVIY KO'RSATKICHLARNI TAHLIL QILISH VA RAQAMLI YECHIMLAR TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH”	586
Azamatjon Mardayev Abdusamat o'g'li	
FARMATSEVIKA MAHSULOTLARI ISHLAB CHIQARUVCHI KORXONALARDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINI TASHKIL ETISHNING ME'YORIY-HUQUQIY ASOSLARI.....	591
Xudaynazarova Dilnoza Gafurovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INNOVASION TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA KADRLAR TAYYORLASH MENEJMENTINING AMAL QILISH USULLARI VA TURLARI	596
Ergashev To'liqin Shokirovich	
HUDUDIIY IQTISODIYOTNI RAQAMLI TEKNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	602
Ibragimov Baxrom Baxodirovich	
ISLOMIY MOLIYA INSTRUMENTLARINI JORIY ETISH ORQALI O'ZBEKISTONDA MOLIYA BOZORINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYA QILISHNING STRATEGIK YO'NALISHLARI.....	606
Xodjayev Aziz Shovkatovich	
MAHALLIY HOKIMIYAT QAROR QABUL QILISH JARAYONLARIDA DINAMIK OMILLAR VA ULARNING INTEGRATSIYASI	611
Axmedov Farxod Raxmonjonovich	
UZOQ MUDDATLI AKTIVLAR AUDITINI TASHKIL ETISH VA TAHLIL QILISH METODLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	617
Rizakulov Abdurauf Abdimutalibovich	
ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ПРИВЛЕКАТЕЛЬНОСТИ ТУРИЗМА ЧЕРЕЗ КРЕАТИВНУЮ ИНДУСТРИЮ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАН.....	623
Хошимова Камилла Навфал қизи	
IMITATION MODELDA AXBOROT NORAVSHANLIGI SABABLI YUZAGA KELADIGAN IQTISODIY SAMARASIZLIK TAHLILI.....	633
Qodirov Zohidjon Eralievich	

JISMONIY SHAXSLAR TOMONIDAN KREDITLARDAN FOYDALANISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI	637
Turdiyeva Kumush Erkinovna	
SOG'LIQNI SAQLASH XIZMATLARI SOHASIDA SIFATNI BAHOLASH KO'RSATKICHLARI VA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIK O'RTASIDAGI BOG'LIQLIK.....	641
Usmanova Nasiba Akbarjonovna, Eshbekova Xayriniso Baxtiyorovna	
SOLIQ TO'LOVCHILAR FAOLIYATINING SEGMENTATSIYASIGA ASOSLANIB SOLIQ XAVFLARINI ANIQLASH VA BAHOLASHNING AMALIY YONDOSHUVI	648
Elbaeva M.R.	
DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHGA TA'SIRI.....	653
Hamroyev G'ayratjon Sultonovich	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI SANOATIDA ISHLAB CHIQRISHNI SIFAT MENEJMENTI TAMOYILLARI ASOSIDA TASHKIL ETISHNING XORIJ MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBASI	657
Achilov Ilmurad	
MINTAQALAR INVESTITSION SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISHNING NAZARIY VA METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI	663
Qobilov Anvar Eshpo'lotovich	
KORXONALARNING YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYASINI ISHLAB CHIQUISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	669
Sapayev Axmed Durdibayevich	
SANOAT KORXONALARINING SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASHDA KO'P MEZONLI TAHLIL USULLARINI QO'LLASH.....	674
Muxammadaliyev Mirzohidjon Muxammadali o'g'li	
BOJXONA HUDUDIDA QAYTA ISHLASH BOJXONA REJIMINING AMALDAGI HOLATI TAHLILI	681
Abdullayev Shaxzodbek	
ENSURING SUSTAINABLE REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT THROUGH INTEGRATION OF RECREATION AND ECOTOURISM RESOURCES IN UZBEKISTAN	686
Shaymanova Nigora Yusupovna	
MAKROIQTISODIYOTDA ISTE'MOL VA JAMG'ARISH FUNSIYALARI VA ULARNING O'ZBEKISTONDA O'ZGARISHI TENDENSIYALARI	691
Rustamov Narzillo Istamovich	
CHAKANA SAVDONI BOSHQARISHDA "BIG MIDDLE" NAZARIYASIDAN FOYDALANISH.....	697
Yaqubov Azizbek G'anibekovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA HUNARMANDCHILIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING PROGNOZ VARIANTLARI.....	701
Ermetov Amirbek Ismailovich	
FISKAL NOMARKAZLASHTIRISH BO'YICHA XITOIY TAJRIBASI.....	708
Lokayev Bekzod Sherkobilovich	
SANOAT KORXONALARIDA RAQAMLI BOSHQARUV TIZIMLARI: IMKONIYATLAR VA CHEKLOVLAR.....	712
Ismatullayeva Munisxon Bori qizi	
EKOLOGIYA VA ATROF MUHITNI MUHOFAZA QILISH SOHASIDA DASTURIY BUDJETLASHTIRISH BO'YICHA XORIJIY MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBASI.....	717
Dilshod Pulatov, Dildora Mirzaeva, Gulzora Qahharova	
TIKUV-TRIKOTAJ SANOATIDA MEHNAT UNUMDORLIGINI OSHIRISH OMILLARI VA BOSHQARUV STRATEGIYALARI.....	725
Mardiyev Bunyod Sirojiddin o'g'li	
BURNOUTNING OLDINI OLIISH: XODIMLAR SALOMATLIGI STRATEGIYASI.....	731
Ergasheva E'zoza Dilshod qizi	
O'ZBEKISTONDA KORXONALARNING TASHQI IQTISODIY FAOLIYATINI MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING HOZIRGI HOLATI VA MUAMMOLARI.....	736
Pulatova Moxira Baxtiyorovna	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI KORXONALARIDA XARAJATLARNI BOSHQARISH VA HISOBGA OLIISHNING INNOVATSION USULLARI: MENEJMENT VA BUXGALTERIYANING O'ZARO INTEGRATSIYASI.....	742
Mamadiyarov Dilshad Uralovich, Normurodov Sarvar Norboy o'g'li	

RIVOJLANGAN MAMLAKATLARDA AHOLI DAROMADLARINI OSHIRISH MEKANIZMLARI.....	748
Uzoqov Suhrobjon Do'smat o'g'li	
OLIY TA'LIMNI MOLIYALASHTIRISH MODELLARI.....	754
Talapova Nargiza Baxriddinovna	
ВОЗОБНОВЛЕНИЕ ДОБЫЧИ ПРИРОДНОГО ГАЗА ИЗ ТРЁХ СКВАЖИН УЧАСТКА ХОДЖАСАЯТ ГКМ ДЕНГИЗКУЛЬ.....	758
Набиев Шахзод Темурович, Иргашбаев Шохрух Фаррух угли, Маннафов Улугбек Умар угли	
MADANIY TURIZM INDUSTRIYASINING RIVOJLANISH IMKONIYATLARI VA O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI.....	764
Toxirov Dilyor Davlatovich	
MOLIYAVIY AUTSORSING NAZARIYALARI VA UNING RIVOJLANISH BOSQICHLARI.....	768
Babadjanov Umidbek Kamildjanovich	
TURIZM – TARIXIY XOTIRA VA ZAMONAVIY XIZMATLAR UYG'UNLIGI IFODASI.....	773
Janzakov Bekzot Kulmamat o'g'li	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI MAHSULOTLARI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINING MOHIYATI VA BAHOLASH MEZONLARI.....	777
Abdikarimova Zilola Baxramovna	
TIJORAT BANKLARI AKTIVLARINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYALASHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	784
Ro'ziyeva Shaxlo Salimboyevna	
AXBOROT TIZIMLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA TEXNIK XIZMAT KO'RSATISHNI QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH.....	788
Samiyeva Maftuna Faxriddin qizi	
TIJORAT BANKLARI AKTIVLARI DAROMADLILIGINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI.....	791
Sanayev Javoxir Shovkat o'g'li	
FISCAL, MONETARY, AND CUSTOMS-TARIFF POLICIES IN ENSURING NATIONAL ECONOMIC STABILITY: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN.....	796
Maxmudov S.T.	
ЗАРУБЕЖНЫЙ ОПЫТ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ И РАЗВИТИЯ ТУРИСТИЧЕСКИХ КЛАСТЕРОВ.....	801
Юсупова Н.Т.	
SANOAT KORXONALARINING IQTISODIY O'SISHIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI ASOSIY FAKTORLAR TAHLILI.....	807
Rahimova Mushtariybegim Muxammadg'olib qizi	
DEMOGRAFIK O'ZGARISHLAR VA ULARNING IJTIMOIIY-IQTISODIY OQIBATLARI.....	812
Abdumalikova G.F.	
MINTAQAVIY INVESTITSIYA SIYOSATINI SAMARALI BOSHQARISHNING IQTISODIY VA INSTITUTSION ASOSLARI.....	821
Kenjayev Ikrom Ergashboyevich	
RAQAMLI AVIATSIYA EKOTIZIMI: AI/ML, DIGITAL TWIN VA BLOKCHEYN INTEGRATSIYASI.....	828
Azimova Moxinur Nozimovna	
XALQARO MOLIYA BOZORLARIDA INVESTITSIYA RISKLARINI BOSHQARISHNING ZAMONAVIY MEKANIZMLARI.....	834
G'afurov Sherzod Abduvaxob o'g'li	
SURXONDARYO VILOYATINING REKREATSIYA RESURLARI VA DAVOLASH-SOG'LOMLASHTIRISH TURIZMI SALOHIYATI.....	839
Murtazayeva Gulrux Isabek qizi	
MINTAQALAR TURISTIK-REKREATSION IMKONIYATLARINI BAHOLASHDA ZAMONAVIY GIS USULLARINI QO'LLASH (SARIOSIYO TUMANI MISOLIDA).....	845
Safarov Manuchexr Axtam o'g'li	
XITOIY TAJRIBASI ASOSIDA INVESTITSIYA MUHITINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	852
Tirkashev Farruxjon Xolyigitovich	
TURIZM FAOLIYATINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYA QILISHGA OID NAZARIY BILIMLARNING SHAKLLANISH XUSUSIYATLARI.....	857
Maxmudova Aziza Pirmamatovna	

TIJORAT BANKLARI RESURS BAZASI MUSTAHKAMLIGINI BAHOLOVCHI KO'RSATKICHLAR TIZIMI	863
Raxmanov Iloxom Xurramovich	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATI KORXONALARIDA BOSHQARUV TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	871
Maxsudov Sherzod Solijonovich	
FISCAL, MONETARY, AND CUSTOMS-TARIFF POLICIES IN ENSURING NATIONAL ECONOMIC STABILITY: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN.....	877
Mahmudov Sarvar	
ATROF-MUHITGA OID FISKAL KO'RSATKICHLAR ASOSIDA MINTAQAVIY BAHOLASH	882
Zilola Rahmatova	
XORAZM VILOYATI TUMANLARIDA EKSPORT SAMARADORLIGI: STOXAСТИK CHEGARAVIY TAHLIL (SFA) ASOSIDAGI EMPIRIK YONDASHUV	887
Fozil Xolmurotov	
МЕТОДИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ОЦЕНКИ БЕДНОСТИ: МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ И НАЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ СПЕЦИФИКА.....	900
Мамаризоев Жахонгир Исохонович	
EKOLOGIK VAZIYAT VA AHOLI SALOMATLIGINING PROGNOZ KO'RSATKICHLARI	905
Egamqulov Husniddin Erkaboyevich	
CHO'L HUDUDLARIDA TURISTIK RESURLARDAN FOYDALANISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	911
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Mavlonov Ahmadjon Muhammadovich	
КОНЦЕПЦИЯ ИДЕНТИФИКАЦИИ И ИЗМЕРЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТОВ ЗАНЯТОСТИ В ЭКОЛОГО-ОРИЕНТИРОВАННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ.....	918
Сагидуллин Фарид Радикович	
ТЕНДЕНЦИИ В РАЗВИТИИ ГОСТИНИЧНОГО БИЗНЕСА В СФЕРЕ ПРОДВИЖЕНИЯ И СБЫТА ТОВАРОВ И УСЛУГ В ИНДУСТРИИ ГОСТЕПРИИМСТВА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН	927
Бабаджанова Лола Шопулатовна	
O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTIDA OZIYQ-OVQATNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGINING ROLI.....	935
G'aniyev Baydulla Toshmurodovich, Bustonov Komiljon Kumakovich	
TURISTIK MINTAQALARNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA MAHALLIY AHOLINING ISHTIROKINI TA'MINLASHNING AYRIM MASALALARI	943
Abduxamidov Sarvar Adxamovich	
TA'LIM KLASTERLARI KONTEKSTIDA BOSHQARUVNING ZAMONAVIY MUAMMOLARI VA STRATEGIK YECHIMLARI: TRIPLE HELIX MODEL ASOSIDA TAHLIL.....	947
Imamova Nilufar Asamutdinovna	
EKOLOGIK TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IQTISODIY ASOSLARI VA ISTIQBOLLARI.....	954
Xamdullayeva Gulhoyo Ergash qizi	
TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI BAHOLASHNING USLUBIY YONDASHUVLARI	960
Sirojiddinov Kamoliddin	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARIDA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	967
Seytimbetov Kabul Serimbetovich	
AGROTADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATINING ASOSIY FUNKSIYALARI VA RIVOJLANISH QONUNIYATLARI.....	971
Nasriddinov Xusanbek Sadriddin o'g'li	
TEMIR YO'L TRANSPORTIDA ENERGIYA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH: QAYTA TIKLANADIGAN ENERGIYA MANBALARI	976
Abdusattorov Abdusamat Sobirovich	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA RESURLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH VA OZIYQ-OVQAT MAHSULOTLARINI ISHLAB CHIQRISHDA MENEJMENT QARORLARINING IQTISODIY TAHLILI	981
Karieva Gulnora Abdullayevna, Normurodov Sarvar Norboy o'g'li	
TA'LIM TIZIMINI MOLIYALASHTIRISHDA O'QUV DASTURLARINING KAPITAL ZICHLIGI	989
Dusanov Salim Mamarasulovich	

QATTIQ CHIQINDILARNI QAYTA ISHLASH KORXONALARIDA INNOVATSION MENEJMENTNING O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI.....	995
Temirov Azizbek Voit o'g'li	
STRATEGIK REJALASHTIRISH ORQALI KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	1002
G.Ya. Muxibova, O.U. Sharifxodjayeva, O. To'rabekova	
ДЕТЕРМИНАНТЫ И ПОСЛЕДСТВИЯ МЕЖРЕГИОНАЛЬНОЙ МОБИЛЬНОСТИ РАБОЧЕЙ СИЛЫ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	1009
Шакаров Зафар Гаффорович	
TURIZM KLASTERLARIDA TIBBIY XIZMATLAR INTEGRATSIYASI: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA O'ZBEKISTON AMALIYOTI	1018
Yazdanova Shohista Tuyg'un qizi, Farxodova Shohnoza Umidbek qizi	
TELEKOMMUNIKATSIYA SOHASI KORXONALARINING INNOVATSION FAOLLIGINI OSHIRUVCHI ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVNI ISHLAB CHIQISH	1027
Xojiyeva Nazokat Davronbekovna	
QAYTA TIKLANADIGAN ENERGIYA MANBALARINING BARQAROR IQTISODIY O'SISHGA TA'SIRI: O'ZBEKISTON MISOLIDA.....	1034
Shodiyeva Zarinnabonu Shodi qizi	
O'ZBEKISTON QURILISH MATERIALLARI SANOATIDA KORPORATIV BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING ISTIQBOLLI YO'NALISHLARI.....	1039
Qurbaniozov Shaxzodbek Karimovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTDA HISOB SIYOSATINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY-USLUBIY ASOSLARI	1044
Qurbanbayev Jurabek Eruvboyevich	
FINTECH TEXNOLOGIYALARI VA ULARNING KORXONA LIKVIDLIGIGA TA'SIRI.....	1048
Karimov Xondamir Jamshid o'g'li	
IMPROVING STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING OF INCOME AND EXPENSES.....	1056
Pardaeva Shakhnoza Abdinabievna	
DIGITAL SKILLS AND ACCOUNTING EDUCATION: NEEDS AND GAPS IN UZBEK HIGHER EDUCATION – CURRICULUM IMPLICATIONS FOR THE DIGITAL AGE	1061
Rustamova Iroda Bahtiyorovna	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING KREDIT XIZMATLARI: ZAMONAVIY TAHLIL VA TARAQQIYOT TENDENSIYALARI.....	1066
Jo'rayeva Zarifa Bahodir qizi	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI KORXONALARINING YUQORI SIFATLI RIVOJLANISHINI TA'MINLASH	1073
Yaxshiyev Shahzod Sherali o'g'li	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH	1079
Kuvotova Dilnora Kaxramonovna	
MAHSULOT, ISH (XIZMAT)LAR TANNARXIGA KIRITILADIGAN MODDIY XARAJATLAR VA ULARNI HUIJATLASHTIRISH.....	1084
Bolibekov Baxtiyor Achilovich, Rahmonqulov Temirbek Eshmamatovich	
AYOLLARNING YETAKCHILIK KOMPETENSIYALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH IMKONIYATLARI VA TO'SIQLARI	1088
Baymuratova Guldjahan Xamdamovna	
INVESTITSIYA FAOLIYATINI MUQOBIL MOLIYALASHTIRISH AMALIY TAHLILI JARAYONLARI.....	1093
Boboqulov Akmal Muborakbekovich	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOB, IQTISODIY TAHLIL VA AUDIT TIZIMLARINI MODERNIZATSIYA QILISH YO'NALISHLARI	1099
To'laganov Ziyovuddin Kamolitdin o'g'li	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT VA UNING IQTISODIY O'SISHDAGI AHMIYATI	1105
Nematullo Zuvaydullaev	

GLOBAL OZIQ-OVQAT TIZIMIDA AQSH IMPORT-EKSPORT SIYOSATI VA UNING MILLIY OZIQ-OVQAT XAVFSIZLIGIGA TA'SIRI	1109
Matjonov Bekjon Ravshonbekovich	
KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIKNING RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI ASOSIY OMILLAR VA IQTISODI SAMARADORLIGI TAHLILI	1115
Axatova Shahnoza	
ЭКОТУРИСТИЧЕСКИЙ ПОТЕНЦИАЛ И РЕСУРСЫ БУХАРСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ.....	1119
Каримова Фотима Абдурасуловна	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT: O'ZBEKISTONDA ELEKTRON SAVDO VA TO'LOV TIZIMLARINING RIVOJLANISHI.....	1124
Toxirov Shodibek Jo'ra o'g'li	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA IPOTEKA KREDITLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA ILG'OR XORIJ TAJRIBALARI VA ULARNI O'ZBEKISTONDA QO'LLASH IMKONIYATLARI.....	1128
Tohirov Muhammad Bobur Tohir o'g'li	
KATTA HAJMLI MA'LUMOTLARDAN OVOZLI XABARLARNI AJRATIB OLIISHDA PARALLEL HISOBLASH ALGORITMLARI VA UNING DASTURIY MAJMUASINI ISHLAB CHIQUISH	1135
Jummayeva Yulduz Achilovna	
MAMLAKATDA NODAVLAT VA NOTIJORAT TASHKIOTLARNI MOLIYAVIY TA'MINLASH MEKANIZMLARI VA ULARNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	1141
Xusanova Gulsum Baxtiyorovna	
TURISTIK KORXONALARDA BREND KAPITALI TUSHUNCHASI VA UNING TARKIBIY ELEMENTLARI	1146
Zufarov Akmal Gulamiddinovich	
IPOTEKA KREDITLARINI MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING ILG'OR XORIJ TAJRIBALARI VA ULARNI O'ZBEKISTONDA QO'LLASH IMKONIYATLARI	1155
Rasulov Doniyor Dilmurod o'g'li	
RIVOJLANAYOTGAN MAMLAKATLARDA SOLIQQA TORTISHNING TARTIBGA SOLISH FUNKSIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA FISKAL SIYOSAT SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	1161
Sulaymonov Farrux Shuxratovich	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON AGRAR TARMOG'IDA TRANSFORMATSION O'ZGARISHLARNING INSTITUTSIONAL MEKANIZMLARI VA ULARNING SAMARADORLIGI.....	1166
Mambetnazarov Baxit Bisenbaevich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA OZIQ-OVQAT SANOATI KORXONALARINI STRATEGIK BOSHQARISHNING DOLZARBLIGI	1171
Turg'unov Muxriddin Mo'ydinjon o'g'li	
TOSHKENT SHAHRIDA SHAHARSOZLIK JARAYONLARINING EKOLOGIK OQIBATLARI	1175
Ashurov Abdulaziz Rustamovich, Olimov Anvarjon Atamirzayevich	
O'ZBEKISTON TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATINING RIVOJLANISH DINAMIKASI VA UNDA XORIJIY INVESTITSİYALARNING ROLI.....	1182
Nazarova A.N.	
XO'JALIK YURITUVCHI SUBYEKTLARDA MOLIYAVIY BOSHQARISHNING AYRIM JIHATLARI.....	1187
Mamatov O'tkir Botir o'g'li	
JANUBI-G'ARBIY O'ZBEKISTONDA CHORVACHILIK TARMOQLARINI PROGNOZ QILISHNING GEOGRAFIK JIHATLARI (NAVOIY VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	1191
Xudoyberdiyeva Iroda Abduxomidovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA DAVLAT MOLIYASINI BOSHQARISHDA G'AZNACHILIK TIZIMINI RAQAMLASHTIRISHNING MOLIYAVIY SAMARADORLIGI.....	1199
Tangrieva Farida Abdugarimovna	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI ISHLAB CHIQUARISH KORXONALARINING IQTISODIY BARQARORLIGIDA INNOVATSION FAOLIYATNING AHAMIYATI	1204
Kurbanova Shaxnoza Yuldashbayevna	
YASHIL MARKETING YONDASHUVI ORQALI KORXONALARDA RESURS SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	1211
Sapayev Axmed Durdibayevich	

АНАЛИЗ И ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ СЕБЕСТОИМОСТИ ПРОДУКЦИИ И РАСХОДОВ НА ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ	1216
Ташмухамедова Карима Саматовна, Якубова Сабина Алишеровна	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA FERMER XO'JALIKLARINI SAMARALI RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	1222
B.B.Seilbekov	
O'ZBEKISTONDA "YASHIL" IQTISODIYOT VA EKOLOGIK BARQARORLIK SIYOSATINI SHAKLLANTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	1226
Sadullayev Rasulbek Palvanbayevich	
ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT STATE OF FOREIGN TRADE ACTIVITY IN UZBEKISTAN'S REGIONS AND FORECASTING REGIONAL FOREIGN TRADE UNDER WTO AND EAEU ACCESSION (BASED ON THE CASE OF KAZAKHSTAN).....	1230
Sitara Tojiqulova Sobirjon qizi	

ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT STATE OF FOREIGN TRADE ACTIVITY IN UZBEKISTAN'S REGIONS AND FORECASTING REGIONAL FOREIGN TRADE UNDER WTO AND EAEU ACCESSION (BASED ON THE CASE OF KAZAKHSTAN)

Sitora Tojiqulova Sobirjon qizi

Master's graduate of the University of World Economy and Diplomacy, specializing in Foreign Economic Activity.

E-mail: sab1rjanovna017@gmail.com

ORCID: 0009-0002-1292-8183

Abstract. In recent years, Uzbekistan's foreign trade has expanded significantly: between 2018 and 2024, total trade turnover increased from USD 33.8 billion to USD 65.9 billion, almost doubling. This growth was driven by favorable global conditions and internal reforms promoting liberalization and competitiveness. Regionally, trade remains concentrated in several key areas: Tashkent city accounts for 35–37% of the country's total trade, mainly machinery and raw materials imports; Navoiy specializes in non-ferrous metals and chemicals; the Fergana Valley focuses on textiles and agriculture; and Samarkand and Bukhara are major producers of food and construction materials.

Kazakhstan's experience demonstrates how simultaneous participation in the WTO and the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU) produced mixed outcomes—enhancing export diversification but increasing dependence on Russia's economy. Using regional panel data for Uzbekistan (2018–2024) and Kazakhstan (2015–2024), this study employs fixed-effects models and ARIMA forecasts to assess regional trade prospects under WTO and EAEU scenarios. The estimates show that in Kazakhstan, a 10% increase in regional GDP raises exports by roughly 10.5% ($\beta_1 \approx 1.05$, $p < 0.01$), while trade inertia is substantial ($\beta_2 \approx 0.62$). For Uzbekistan, export dynamics display similar persistence. Forecasts for 2025–2029 indicate stable export growth, with WTO membership expected to raise total exports by 4–5% annually and imports by 6–7%, leading to a temporary widening of the trade deficit.

Overall, WTO accession appears strategically more beneficial for Uzbekistan in the long run, supporting export diversification, industrial modernization, and foreign investment attraction. Meanwhile, EAEU membership offers short-term advantages in regional logistics but entails higher dependency risks. Thus, WTO membership should serve as Uzbekistan's primary integration priority, while regional alliances play a complementary role.

Key words: Uzbekistan, regional trade, foreign trade, exports, imports, WTO accession, EAEU membership, Kazakhstan comparison, panel data, econometric modeling, trade forecasting, regional disparities, GDP elasticity, trade policy, import dependence, export diversification, SME competitiveness, logistics infrastructure, industrial modernization, trade integration.

Annotatsiya. So'nggi yillarda O'zbekistonning tashqi savdosi sezilarli darajada kengaydi: 2018–2024-yillar oralig'ida umumiy tashqi savdo hajmi 33,8 milliard AQSh dollaridan 65,9 milliard dollarga yetib, qariyb ikki barobar oshdi. Ushbu o'sish qulay xalqaro sharoitlar hamda liberallashtirish va raqobatbardoshlikni kuchaytirishga qaratilgan ichki islohotlar natijasidir. Hududiy kesimda savdo faoliyati asosan ayrim yirik markazlarda to'plangan: Toshkent shahri mamlakat tashqi savdosining 35–37 foizini tashkil etib, asosan mashinasozlik va xomashyo importiga ixtisoslashgan; Navoiy rangli metallar va kimyo mahsulotlariga; Farg'ona vodiysi to'qimachilik va qishloq xo'jaligiga; Samarqand va Buxoro esa oziq-ovqat hamda qurilish materiallari ishlab chiqarishga ixtisoslashgan.

Qozog'iston tajribasi shuni ko'rsatadiki, Jahon savdo tashkiloti (WTO) va Yevroosiyo iqtisodiy ittifoqiga (EAEU) a'zolik bir vaqtda ijobiy va cheklovchi omillarni yuzaga keltirgan: eksport diversifikatsiyasi kengaydi, biroq Rossiya iqtisodiyotiga bog'liqlik oshdi. Tadqiqotda O'zbekiston (2018–2024) va Qozog'iston (2015–2024) uchun hududiy panel ma'lumotlar asosida sobit effektli modellardan va ARIMA prognozlaridan foydalanildi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, Qozog'istonda hududiy YAİM 10 foizga oshganda, eksport hajmi o'rtacha 10,5 foizga ortadi ($\beta_1 \approx 1.05$, $p < 0.01$), savdo inertsiyasi esa yuqori ($\beta_2 \approx 0.62$). O'zbekistonda eksport dinamikasi o'xshash barqarorlikni namoyon etmoqda. 2025–2029-yillar uchun prognozlarga ko'ra, eksport barqaror o'sishda davom etadi, WTOga a'zolik yillik eksportni 4–5 foizga, importni esa 6–7 foizga oshiradi. Bu qisqa muddatda tashqi savdo balansining vaqtinchalik salbiylashishiga olib keladi.

Umuman olganda, WTOga a'zolik O'zbekiston uchun uzoq muddatda strategik jihatdan foydaliroq bo'lib, eksportni diversifikatsiya qilish, sanoatni modernizatsiya qilish va xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etishni qo'llab-quvvatlaydi. Shu bilan birga, EAEUga a'zolik qisqa muddatda mintaqaviy logistika afzalliklarini taqdim etadi, ammo iqtisodiy bog'liqlik xavfini oshiradi. Shunday qilib, O'zbekiston uchun WTO a'zoligi asosiy integratsion ustuvorlik bo'lishi, EAEU esa qo'shimcha mintaqaviy hamkorlik platformasi sifatida qaralishi maqsadga muvofiqdir.

Kalit so'zlar: O'zbekiston, hududiy savdo, tashqi savdo, eksport, import, WTO a'zoligi, EAEU a'zoligi, Qozog'iston tajribasi, panel ma'lumotlar, iqtisodiy modellashtirish, savdo prognozi, hududiy tafovutlar, YAİM elastikligi, savdo siyosati, importga bog'liqlik, eksport diversifikatsiyasi, KOB raqobatbardoshligi, logistika infratuzilmasi, sanoat modernizatsiyasi, savdo integratsiyasi.

Аннотация. В последние годы внешняя торговля Узбекистана значительно расширилась: за период с 2018 по 2024 год общий объём торговли увеличился с 33,8 до 65,9 млрд долларов США, почти в два раза. Этот рост был обусловлен благоприятными мировыми условиями и внутренними реформами, направленными на либерализацию и повышение конкурентоспособности. В региональном разрезе торговая активность сосредоточена в нескольких ключевых зонах: город Ташкент обеспечивает 35–37% внешней торговли страны (в основном импорт машин и сырья); Навоий специализируется на цветных металлах и химической продукции; Ферганская долина — на текстиле и сельском хозяйстве; Самарканд и Бухара — на производстве продуктов питания и строительных материалов.

Опыт Казахстана показывает, что одновременное участие в ВТО и Евразийском экономическом союзе (ЕАЭС) имеет смешанные результаты: оно способствует диверсификации экспорта, но усиливает зависимость от российской экономики. В исследовании использованы панельные региональные данные по Узбекистану (2018–2024) и Казахстану (2015–2024), а также модели с фиксированными эффектами и прогнозы ARIMA. Результаты показывают, что в Казахстане рост регионального ВВП на 10% увеличивает экспорт примерно на 10,5% ($\beta_1 \approx 1.05$, $p < 0.01$), при этом сохраняется высокая инерционность торговли ($\beta_2 \approx 0.62$). В Узбекистане экспортные тенденции демонстрируют схожую устойчивость. Прогнозы на 2025–2029 годы свидетельствуют о стабильном росте экспорта: членство в ВТО может увеличить экспорт на 4–5% и импорт на 6–7% в год, что приведёт к временному расширению торгового дефицита.

В целом, присоединение к ВТО в долгосрочной перспективе более выгодно для Узбекистана, так как способствует диверсификации экспорта, модернизации промышленности и привлечению иностранных инвестиций. Членство в ЕАЭС обеспечивает краткосрочные преимущества в региональной логистике, но связано с риском повышенной зависимости. Следовательно, членство в ВТО должно стать приоритетом интеграционной стратегии Узбекистана, а участие в ЕАЭС — выполнять вспомогательную роль.

Ключевые слова: Узбекистан, региональная торговля, внешняя торговля, экспорт, импорт, ВТО, ЕАЭС, Казахстан, панельные данные, эконометрическое моделирование, прогнозирование торговли, региональные различия, эластичность ВВП, торговая политика, зависимость от импорта, диверсификация экспорта, конкурентоспособность МСП, логистическая инфраструктура, промышленная модернизация, торговая интеграция.

INTRODUCTION

Uzbekistan's regional foreign trade activities have shown a remarkable upward trajectory in recent years. Between 2018 and 2024, the country's total foreign trade turnover increased from USD 33.8 billion to USD 65.9 billion, nearly doubling within six years. This impressive growth reflects both favorable global market conditions and the government's consistent policies aimed at economic liberalization and trade competitiveness [1].

Regional trade dynamics across Uzbekistan demonstrate distinct structural patterns and varying degrees of specialization. For instance, Tashkent City accounts for approximately 35–37% of the country's total trade

volume, primarily due to its high concentration of imports. Meanwhile, regions such as Navoi and Bukhara specialize in mining, metallurgy, and chemical production, whereas the Fergana Valley focuses on textiles, agriculture, and automotive industries [2].

LITERATURE REVIEW

Existing literature provides valuable insights into the dynamics of regional trade and integration processes. Scholars such as Abdurakhmonov (2020) and Mingishov (2020) have analyzed Uzbekistan's foreign trade structure, identifying regional disparities while emphasizing the necessity of coordinated export–import strategies [6]. Abdurakhmonov (2020) examines the institutional and structural dimensions of Uzbekistan's trade system and proposes a long-term framework for development, whereas Mingishov (2020) explores the evolution of regional trade trends across Central Asian economies [7].

However, comprehensive empirical research assessing the potential effects of Uzbekistan's prospective accession to the World Trade Organization (WTO) and the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU) on regional trade remains limited. This study seeks to address this research gap by conducting a comparative analysis of Uzbekistan's regional foreign trade patterns and forecasting potential developments under WTO and EAEU accession scenarios, using Kazakhstan's experience as a reference point [8].

The main objectives of this study are as follows:

To analyze the dynamics of regional foreign trade in Uzbekistan from 2018 to 2024.

To assess the potential effects of WTO and EAEU accession on regional trade flows.

To propose policy recommendations aimed at strengthening regional trade integration and sustainable growth.

The research hypothesis suggests that Uzbekistan's accession to the WTO will generate long-term strategic advantages, including export diversification, industrial modernization, and deeper integration into global markets. Conversely, EAEU membership may provide short-term regional trade and infrastructure benefits, yet it could also increase structural economic interdependence with the Russian market [9].

Methodologically, the study applies regional panel data analysis, econometric modeling, and scenario-based forecasting — incorporating WTO, EAEU, and combined interaction effects — to evaluate potential outcomes of Uzbekistan's trade integration policies.

Analysis of the Current State of Foreign Trade Activities in Uzbekistan's Regions

In recent years, Uzbekistan's foreign trade turnover has demonstrated a sustained and remarkable upward trajectory. Between 2018 and 2024, the country's total foreign trade volume expanded from USD 33.8 billion to USD 65.9 billion, nearly doubling within six years [1]. This substantial growth has been driven by two principal factors: first, favorable shifts in global market conditions, and second, the implementation of consistent liberalization reforms in national foreign economic policy, which have collectively strengthened the openness, efficiency, and competitiveness of the country's external trade system.

Regional Export–Import Patterns

Across the regions, Uzbekistan's foreign trade structure reveals notable differences in specialization and trade intensity:

Tashkent City accounts for approximately 35–37% of the country's total foreign trade volume, with a dominant share of imports — primarily industrial machinery, vehicles, and raw materials.

Navoiy Region has recently strengthened its export position through the supply of gold, non-ferrous metals, and chemical products.

The Fergana Valley (including Fergana, Andijan, and Namangan) is distinguished by the export of textiles, agricultural produce, and automotive products.

Samarkand and Bukhara Regions remain major exporters of foodstuffs, textiles, and construction materials [10].

For comparative perspective, Kazakhstan's regional foreign trade is led by Atyrau, Mangistau, and Karaganda, regions that primarily export oil, gas, and metals. This comparison underscores that while Uzbekistan's trade is becoming increasingly diversified across its regions, Kazakhstan's trade remains more concentrated in resource-based sectors.

Regarding the export–import balance, Tashkent City and industrialized regions such as Andijan and Fergana are characterized by import-dominant trade, whereas Navoiy and Qashqadaryo demonstrate strong export performance. This pattern reflects the asymmetric structure of interregional trade, influenced by variations in industrial specialization, production capacity, and access to external markets.

Kazakhstan's experience further illustrates that integration into the World Trade Organization (WTO) and the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU) can significantly transform regional trade flows. Some regions rapidly

enhance their export capacity through improved access to external markets, while others undergo gradual adaptation to new competitive conditions. For Uzbekistan, this offers a valuable analytical framework, as the country's regions differ considerably in terms of natural resources, industrial diversification, and transport–logistics infrastructure.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study first examines the current state of regional foreign trade across Uzbekistan and then evaluates the potential effects of WTO and EAEU accession on regional export–import flows, using Kazakhstan's integration experience as a comparative model. The analysis is supported by quantitative and econometric modeling tools.

Key methodological approaches include:

Comparative analysis — examining Kazakhstan's regional trade patterns following WTO and EAEU membership to identify relevant policy pathways for Uzbekistan.

Econometric modeling — constructing regression and forecasting models for exports and imports that account for variables such as external demand, global prices, and customs regimes.

Scenario analysis — developing most probable, optimistic, and conservative projections for regional trade performance under WTO and EAEU membership conditions.

Rationale for Regional Trade Analysis

The necessity of detailed regional foreign trade analysis in Uzbekistan is determined by three interrelated factors:

High interregional disparities, with Tashkent City dominating overall trade volumes, while several regions remain more domestically oriented.

Dependence on raw material exports, which highlights the need for industrial diversification and higher value-added production.

The strategic necessity of market diversification, aimed at reducing overreliance on a limited number of trading partners and expanding access to new international markets.

Key indicators in this analysis include regional export and import volumes, their dynamics, structural composition, and the share of trade in each region's Gross Regional Product (GRP). These metrics collectively help to evaluate the sustainability, inclusivity, and growth potential of Uzbekistan's regional foreign trade system.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Analysis of Current Foreign Trade in Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan

Data and Variables.

Annual regional export and import data for Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan covering the period 2018–2024 were analyzed. Uzbekistan's data were obtained from the State Committee of Statistics (annual trade reports; sources are listed in the appendix), while Kazakhstan's data were taken from the National Statistics Bureau through the interactive “Regional Foreign Trade Turnover” tables available at stat.gov.kz.

All trade indicators were converted to constant U.S. dollars (USD) using each country's GDP deflator (World Bank/IMF) with 2020 as the base year. For Uzbekistan, the Consumer Price Index (CPI) was additionally cross-checked to ensure data consistency. Exchange rates (local currency per USD) were taken from IMF International Financial Statistics and used to convert nominal values to constant USD based on annual averages.

The panel dataset was structured by region-year and included the following variables: Region, Year, Exports, Imports (in constant USD), and, where available, Gross Regional Product (GRP). For Uzbekistan, regional GRP data were sourced from national accounts, while for Kazakhstan they were taken from official statistical yearbooks. Since consistent annual GRP series were unavailable for Uzbekistan, GRP was excluded from its regression models; it was incorporated only for Kazakhstan. Other regional indicators (such as population and FDI inflows) were omitted due to data inconsistency, allowing the analysis to focus primarily on trade flows and macroeconomic factors.

Descriptive Statistics.

Across all regions and years, Uzbekistan's regions recorded an average of approximately USD 1.8 billion in exports ($\sigma \approx 1.7$) and USD 2.8 billion in imports ($\sigma \approx 2.5$). In comparison, Kazakhstan's regional averages were notably higher — around USD 4.8 billion in exports ($\sigma \approx 4.0$) and USD 3.5 billion in imports ($\sigma \approx 3.0$). These figures reflect Kazakhstan's larger and more diversified trade structure as well as its stronger integration into global markets (Table 1).

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of Regional Trade (Average, Standard Deviation, Minimum, and Maximum Values in Million USD)

Country	Trade Type	Average (mln USD)	SD (mln USD)	Min (mln USD)	Max (mln USD)
Uzbekistan	Export	1,800	1,700	30	5,500
Uzbekistan	Import	2,800	2,500	200	12,000
Kazakhstan	Export	4,800	4,000	50	36,000
Kazakhstan	Import	3,500	3,000	100	15,000

Note. Values are calculated for all regions and years covering the period 2018–2024. Prepared by the author based on the official statistics of Uzbekistan (www.stat.gov.uz) (Last accessed: 2025–09–11).

Minimal regional exports in several smaller Uzbek regions were close to zero, whereas the maximum export volume exceeded USD 13 billion (Uzbekistan: min \approx 0.03, max \approx 13.6; Kazakhstan: min \approx 0.05, max \approx 36).

This observation confirms that Kazakhstan's foreign trade is not only larger in absolute terms but also more regionally diversified, while Uzbekistan's trade remains relatively smaller on average yet highly concentrated in key economic hubs — notably Tashkent, which accounts for approximately 20–30 % of total national trade.

National Figures (2024).

Uzbekistan's total foreign trade turnover reached USD 65.9 billion, of which USD 26.9 billion represented exports and USD 39.0 billion imports.

Within this structure, Tashkent alone contributed USD 5.5 billion in exports (20.5 % of national total) and USD 19.8 billion in imports (50.8 %), clearly demonstrating the capital city's dominant role in the country's trade landscape.

In comparison, Kazakhstan's total trade volume in 2024 amounted to USD 141.4 billion (exports = USD 81.6 billion; imports = USD 59.8 billion). Major exporting regions such as Atyrau and Mangistau each contributed tens of billions of USD, while some northern regions recorded exports of only a few hundred million USD.

This disparity indicates that Kazakhstan's trade structure is characterized by resource-based regional specialization, whereas Uzbekistan's trade, though expanding, is diversifying through industrial and service-sector growth.

Empirical Strategy

To assess regional determinants of foreign trade performance, separate panel regressions were estimated for exports and imports, incorporating region-specific fixed effects.

For each country (C), the following log-linear specification was adopted:

$$\ln(\text{Trade}_{it}) = \alpha + \beta_1 \ln(\text{GDP}_{it}) + \beta_2 \ln(\text{Trade}_{i,t-1}) + \beta_3 \text{ExchRate}_t + \beta_4 \text{WTODummy}_t + \beta_5 \text{CISDummy}_t + \mu_i + \lambda_t + \epsilon_{it}$$

where:

$\text{Trade}_{(it)}$ — represents the export or import volume of region i in year t ;

$\text{GDP}_{(it)}$ — denotes the regional Gross Domestic Product (available only for Kazakhstan);

ExchRate_t — the nominal exchange rate (USD per local currency unit), reflecting the effects of currency depreciation;

WTODummy_t — equals 1 for years following WTO accession and 0 otherwise (for Kazakhstan: $t \geq 2016$, since the country joined the WTO on 30 November 2015; for Uzbekistan: $\text{WTODummy}_t = 0$, as the country has not yet acceded);

CISDummy_t — equals 1 for years following accession to the CIS Free Trade Area (Kazakhstan: effective 2012; Uzbekistan: joined via protocol in 2014);

μ_i — captures region-specific fixed effects, controlling for unobserved heterogeneity;

λ_t — represents year-specific dummies accounting for time-varying macroeconomic shocks;

$\epsilon_{(it)}$ — is the idiosyncratic error term.

Both fixed-effects (FE) and random-effects (RE) specifications were initially estimated to identify the most appropriate model.

However, results of the Hausman test consistently favored the fixed-effects model at a high level of statistical significance ($p < 0.01$).

Therefore, all final estimates were obtained using the FE model, with standard errors clustered at the regional level to ensure robustness against potential heteroskedasticity and serial correlation.

Panel Unit Root Testing and Regression Estimation

Prior to estimation, panel unit root tests (modified Im–Pesaran–Shin, IPS) were conducted to verify the stationarity of the series.

The results indicated that export and import series were non-stationary in levels but stationary in first differences. Accordingly, where required, differenced models or error-correction specifications were applied.

However, considering the relatively short time dimension of the dataset ($T \approx 7$ years), the analysis primarily relied on logarithmic fixed-effects (FE) models.

To prevent spurious regressions, residuals were tested for stationarity using the Pesaran cross-sectional dependence (CD) test, which did not reject the null hypothesis of stationarity ($p > 0.1$). Additionally, year fixed effects were included to absorb common global shocks and time-specific disturbances.

Panel Regression Results

All estimated models incorporated one-year lagged trade volume to capture trade inertia, along with the exchange rate variable.

Export Models

The estimated GDP elasticity (β_1) was found to be positive and statistically significant.

In Kazakhstan's export model, $\beta_1 \approx 1.05$ (standard error ≈ 0.15 , $p < 0.01$), suggesting that a doubling of regional GDP is associated with an almost proportional (1:1) increase in exports.

The lagged export coefficient ($\beta_2 \approx 0.62$, $p < 0.05$) indicates strong persistence in regional export growth, confirming that previous-year trade performance significantly influences current export outcomes.

The exchange rate coefficient (β_3) was small and statistically insignificant (≈ 0.10 – 0.15 for Kazakhstan), implying that local currency depreciation slightly boosts exports in nominal terms but has a minimal effect when measured in constant USD.

The WTO dummy (β_4) was positive for Kazakhstan's exports (≈ 0.04 , $p < 0.10$), suggesting that post-2015 WTO membership contributed to a moderate increase of around 4 % in export volumes. This variable was not applicable to Uzbekistan, where $WTODummy_t = 0$ for all years.

The CIS dummy ($\beta_5 \approx 0.02$), effective for Kazakhstan from 2012, was small and statistically insignificant, indicating that CIS Free Trade Area participation had a limited direct effect on export dynamics.

The overall within- R^2 for the export models equaled 0.82 for Kazakhstan and 0.85 for Uzbekistan, reflecting a strong explanatory power of the regression models.

Model diagnostics — including Breusch–Pagan and Wooldridge tests — confirmed the absence of heteroskedasticity after clustering, while Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values below 3 indicated no multicollinearity concerns.

Import Models

Results for imports exhibited similar patterns.

Regional GDP was positively associated with imports (where data were available), and the lagged import coefficient ($\beta_2 \approx 0.7$) confirmed the presence of import persistence.

The exchange rate remained statistically insignificant in most cases, reflecting that imports — typically priced in foreign currencies — are less sensitive to short-term exchange rate fluctuations.

No statistically significant WTO effect was observed on imports.

For Uzbekistan, imports demonstrated stability during 2020–2024, with an average annual growth rate of around 0.8 %, while time fixed effects successfully captured global disturbances such as oil price fluctuations.

Once again, the Hausman test strongly favored the fixed-effects specification over random effects.

Cointegration and Error-Correction Analysis

Given the presence of trends in trade variables, panel unit root and cointegration tests were additionally performed.

While several series were non-stationary, the Levin–Lin–Chu test on residuals from the regression of RegGDP and Trade (for Kazakhstan) failed to reject cointegration, confirming the existence of long-run equilibrium relationships.

Consequently, an Error Correction Model (ECM) was estimated, regressing the change in trade ($\Delta \ln \text{Trade}$) on the change in GDP ($\Delta \ln \text{GDP}$) and lagged deviations from equilibrium.

The ECM results were consistent with the FE estimates — short-term elasticity $\beta_{\Delta \text{GDP}} \approx 0.9$, and long-term adjustment parameter $\alpha \approx 1.1$.

Given the similarity of outcomes and the relatively limited time span, the logarithmic FE model was retained as the main analytical framework due to its robustness and interpretability.

Forecasting Analysis (Using Time Series Models)

In the next analytical stage, short-term forecasts for 2025–2029 were generated for the largest trading regions in both Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan using univariate time series models. Based on the 2024 dataset, the leading exporting regions were identified as follows:

Uzbekistan: Tashkent, Navoi, Fergana, Andijan, and Samarkand;

Kazakhstan: Atyrau, Mangistau, Karaganda, East Kazakhstan, and Pavlodar.

Each region's export and import time series was tested for stationarity.

Results from the Augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) tests generally indicated the presence of a single unit root, suggesting first-difference stationarity. Therefore, first-differenced models or ARDL models with error-correction (ECM) terms were applied.

Optimal lag lengths were determined using the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC).

For example:

Tashkent exports were best fitted using a log-ARDL(1,1) model;

Atyrau exports followed an ARIMA(1,1,1) specification.

The in-sample fit of all models was satisfactory, with Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) values averaging 3–5% of the series mean, indicating strong model precision and consistency.

Error-Correction Model (Kazakhstan Case: Short- and Long-Term Effects)

$$\Delta \ln(\text{Export}_{it}) = \phi [\ln(\text{GDP}_{i,t-1}) - 1.10 \ln(\text{Export}_{i,t-1})] + 0.90 \Delta \ln(\text{GDP}_{it}) + 0.25 \Delta \ln(\text{Export}_{i,t-1}) + \text{other terms} + u_{it}$$

The error-correction coefficient ($\phi \approx -0.30$, s.e. = 0.08, $p < 0.01$) indicates the speed of adjustment toward long-run equilibrium.

The short-term GDP elasticity is approximately 0.90 (s.e. = 0.25), while the long-term elasticity is 1.10.

Interpretation:

When exports deviate from their long-term equilibrium, approximately 30% of the disequilibrium is corrected within each subsequent period. Moreover, a 1% short-term increase in regional GDP leads to a 0.9% rise in exports, confirming a stable positive relationship between production output and trade performance.

Additional Statistical Indicators and Data Coverage

Sample Size:

Uzbekistan — 16 regions × 7 years ≈ 112 region-year observations;

Kazakhstan — 16–18 regions × 7 years ≈ 112–126 observations.

Hausman Test: $p < 0.01$ → Fixed Effects model preferred.

Panel Unit Root Tests: Non-stationary in levels → Stationary in first differences → ECM or differenced models applied.

These results confirm that the panel data structure and econometric specifications are statistically valid and robust for both countries.

Interpretation of Estimated Coefficients

For Kazakhstan, the estimated coefficients are as follows:

$\beta_1 = 1.05$ → A 10% increase in regional GDP leads to an approximate 10.5% rise in exports.

$\beta_2 = 0.62$ → Export shocks demonstrate strong persistence, with around 62% of the previous year's change carrying over to the next.

WTO Dummy ($\beta_4 \approx 0.04$) → Following Kazakhstan's WTO accession, export volumes increased by roughly 4%, indicating a modest but positive structural impact (see Table 2).

Overall, these results support the hypothesis that trade liberalization and economic integration promote sustainable export expansion, particularly in regions with high industrial and resource capacity.

Model Accuracy and Forecast Reliability

For Uzbekistan, regional export models achieved RMSE ≈ 0.2–0.3 (log scale) in holdout validation tests.

For Kazakhstan, the results were similar, confirming model stability.

Wider confidence intervals were observed for oil-dependent regions such as Atyrau and Mangistau, reflecting greater exposure to global price volatility.

All forecasts were constructed under the “no structural disruption” assumption, implying the absence of unexpected macroeconomic or geopolitical shocks during 2025–2029.

These projections provide a reliable short-term outlook for regional trade trends and offer valuable insight for policymakers to develop adaptive export strategies based on regional specialization and resilience (Table 2).

Table 2. Export Forecast for the Five Largest Regions, 2025–2029 (USD Billion, 95% Confidence Interval)

Region	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
Tashkent (UZ)	6.10 (5.80–6.40)	6.50 (6.20–6.80)	6.80 (6.50–7.10)	7.10 (6.80–7.40)	7.30 (7.00–7.60)
Navoi (UZ)	1.20 (1.10–1.30)	1.25 (1.15–1.35)	1.30 (1.20–1.40)	1.35 (1.25–1.45)	1.40 (1.30–1.50)
Fergana (UZ)	0.90 (0.80–1.00)	0.95 (0.85–1.05)	1.00 (0.90–1.10)	1.05 (0.95–1.15)	1.10 (1.00–1.20)
Andijan (UZ)	1.50 (1.30–1.70)	1.55 (1.35–1.75)	1.60 (1.40–1.80)	1.65 (1.45–1.85)	1.70 (1.50–1.90)
Samarkand (UZ)	1.80 (1.60–2.00)	1.85 (1.65–2.05)	1.90 (1.70–2.10)	1.95 (1.75–2.15)	2.00 (1.80–2.20)
Atyrau (KZ)	34.00 (32.50–35.50)	35.00 (33.50–36.50)	36.00 (34.50–37.50)	37.00 (35.50–38.50)	38.00 (36.50–39.50)
Mangystau (KZ)	17.00 (16.20–17.80)	17.50 (16.70–18.30)	18.00 (17.20–18.80)	18.50 (17.70–19.30)	19.00 (18.20–19.80)
Karaganda (KZ)	8.50 (7.90–9.10)	8.80 (8.20–9.40)	9.00 (8.40–9.60)	9.20 (8.60–9.80)	9.40 (8.80–10.00)
East Kazakhstan (KZ)	4.00 (3.70–4.30)	4.20 (3.90–4.50)	4.40 (4.10–4.70)	4.50 (4.20–4.80)	4.60 (4.30–4.90)
Pavlodar (KZ)	3.50 (3.20–3.80)	3.60 (3.30–3.90)	3.70 (3.40–4.00)	3.80 (3.50–4.10)	3.90 (3.60–4.20)

Note. Forecasts are presented with 95% confidence intervals based on the estimated econometric models. Prepared by the author based on analytical results.

Date of preparation: 2025–09–12.

Membership Scenarios and Model Evaluation WTO and CIS Membership Effects

The WTO dummy variable demonstrated a small but positive effect on Kazakhstan's exports ($\beta_4 \approx +0.04$ since 2016). Based on this result, if Uzbekistan were to accede to the World Trade Organization (WTO) starting from 2025, its export forecasts would likely increase by approximately 4–5 %.

For instance, under WTO membership, Tashkent's 2029 export forecast would rise from the baseline USD 7.3 billion to around USD 7.6 billion, illustrating the potential incremental trade benefits of global market integration.

As for the CIS Free Trade Area, since both countries were already members (Kazakhstan since 2012, Uzbekistan since 2014), no additional structural impact was observed after 2018.

Furthermore, structural break tests (Chow tests for 2015–2016) did not indicate statistically significant discontinuities ($p > 0.1$), suggesting stability in post-accession trade dynamics.

Model Evaluation and Diagnostics

Model Fit: The panel models exhibited a slightly better fit for Uzbekistan, with higher R^2 values and lower RMSE, confirming model robustness.

Volatility: Kazakhstan's export patterns displayed higher volatility due to commodity price cycles, particularly in oil-dependent regions.

Key Drivers:

GDP elasticity ≈ 1.0 , implying proportional responsiveness of exports to economic growth.

Trade inertia $\approx 0.6–0.7$, indicating persistence in trade activity over time.

Exchange Rate: Statistically insignificant, as data were denominated in USD, reducing direct currency effects.

Institutional Factors: WTO membership produced a small yet positive “market access and institutional trust” effect for Kazakhstan.

Stationarity: ADF tests confirmed unit roots in most level series; however, panel cointegration tests did not reject long-run relationships between GDP and exports.

Robustness Checks: Alternative estimations — including random-effects (RE) models, first-difference transformations, and specifications excluding the exchange rate — yielded consistent results, reinforcing model reliability.

Comparative Interpretation

Uzbekistan's export growth remains steady and moderately paced, with Tashkent maintaining the leading contribution to total exports.

By contrast, Kazakhstan's total export volume is substantially higher but more dependent on global oil and metal prices, making it susceptible to external fluctuations.

Despite this, the overall forecasts for 2025–2029 suggest stable upward trends in both countries, underpinned by improved trade efficiency and regional diversification.

If Uzbekistan completes WTO accession, empirical estimates predict an additional ~5 % export growth advantage, attributable to increased market access, reduced trade barriers, and enhanced investor confidence.

Econometric Framework and Data Sources

The forecasting model integrates regional panel data on exports and imports for:

Uzbekistan (2018–2024) — data sourced from stat.uz;

Kazakhstan (2015–2024) — data from stat.gov.kz.

Explanatory variables include:

Regional GDP, population, industrial output, foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows, and sectoral specialization indices.

Panel regressions with fixed effects control for region-specific unobserved heterogeneity, while ARIMA time-series models capture overarching trade dynamics.

Together, these methods ensure both cross-sectional accuracy and temporal predictive validity.

Scenario Analysis Based on Kazakhstan's Experience

Kazakhstan's regional trade performance provides a valuable benchmark for Uzbekistan under three prospective integration paths:

WTO Accession Scenario — tariff reductions and liberalized market access accelerate trade growth;

EAEU-Dominant Scenario — preferential trade remains regionally concentrated within the Eurasian Economic Union;

Combined Scenario (WTO + EAEU) — multilateral integration balancing global and regional trade networks.

Empirical evidence shows that after joining the WTO, Kazakhstan's exports grew by an average of 5.2 % per year, while imports increased by 7.1 %, with export growth concentrated in hydrocarbon-rich regions, slightly widening regional disparities.

Projected Implications for Uzbekistan

Applying these coefficients to Uzbekistan's trade structure suggests that, under WTO accession, total exports could grow by 4.8–5.5 % per year in the medium term (2025–2029).

Industrial and service-oriented regions are expected to record faster growth, while imports may increase by 6–7 %, reflecting higher demand for foreign goods and technologies amid greater competition.

Overall, WTO membership would provide Uzbekistan with a strategic advantage in expanding exports, diversifying markets, and deepening global economic integration — reinforcing the long-term sustainability of its trade development model.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The regional forecasts demonstrate differentiated yet mutually reinforcing effects across Uzbekistan's regions. In Tashkent, re-export operations, service sector expansion, and logistics development are expected to accelerate annual trade turnover by approximately 8–9 %. The Navoiy and Bukhara regions are projected to gain notable advantages through industrial exports associated with mining, metallurgy, and chemical production, while the Fergana Valley (Fergana, Andijan, Namangan) is likely to sustain stable import growth driven by increasing consumer demand and agricultural modernization.

The econometric model further indicates that, under a WTO-only accession scenario, Uzbekistan may experience a temporary widening of the trade deficit due to the liberalization of import tariffs and the inflow of new goods. However, under a combined WTO + EAEU scenario, the interaction of global market access with regional tariff preferences could offset such imbalances, resulting in a more harmonized and sustainable regional trade structure.

Overall, the comparative econometric findings suggest that Uzbekistan's regional economies are institutionally and structurally prepared for deeper international integration following potential accession to the WTO and EAEU. To fully realize the benefits of both global and regional integration, it is essential for policymakers to:

- promote export diversification beyond raw materials,
- expand logistics and digital infrastructure, and

implement region-specific trade and industrial policies that strengthen the competitiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs).

The experience of Kazakhstan provides valuable insights into potential outcomes for Uzbekistan. Kazakhstan's WTO accession facilitated long-term strategic gains, including enhanced export diversification, broader global market access, and increased foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows. Simultaneously, membership in the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU) supported regional trade and infrastructure integration, though it also led to greater sensitivity to Russia's economic cycles.

From a strategic perspective, WTO membership offers sustainable, long-term benefits for Uzbekistan—particularly in promoting industrial modernization, technological upgrading, and integration into global value chains. In contrast, the EAEU can yield short-term practical advantages, especially in regional logistics, customs harmonization, and cross-border transport projects. Nonetheless, these benefits must be managed prudently to ensure economic independence and balanced interregional development.

In conclusion, WTO accession should be regarded as Uzbekistan's foremost strategic priority in external economic policy, serving as a foundation for export diversification, industrial transformation, and international investment attraction. Meanwhile, participation in regional economic unions such as the EAEU should function as a complementary mechanism, reinforcing Uzbekistan's broader goal of achieving sustainable, inclusive, and globally competitive trade integration.

REFERENCES

1. Uzbekistan Statistical Agency. External Trade Turnover Reports (2018–2024). Available at: <https://stat.uz> (last accessed: September 10, 2025).
2. World Bank. (2023). Uzbekistan Economic Update: Navigating Reforms. Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org> (last accessed: September 10, 2025).
3. OECD. (2022). Trade Policy Reviews: Kazakhstan 2016–2021 – Post-WTO Membership Assessment. Available at: <https://www.oecd.org> (last accessed: September 12, 2025).
4. Kadyrova, D., & Mukhamedov, A. (2023). Regional Trade Competitiveness under WTO Accession: Evidence from Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan. *Central Asian Economic Review*, 25 (2), 55–73.
5. International Monetary Fund (IMF). (2024). World Economic Outlook Database. Available at: <https://www.imf.org> (last accessed: September 12, 2025).
6. Abdurakhmonov, A. (May 2020). The Current Status of Uzbekistan's Import/Export Trading System and Suggested Future Development Plan. Inha University in Tashkent. DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30002.94404.
7. Mingishov, L. (December 2020). Analysis of Regional Trade Development Trends in Central Asian Countries (Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan). University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED), Tashkent.
8. World Bank, WITS Data Portal. Uzbekistan Trade Statistics. Available at: <https://wits.worldbank.org> (last accessed: September 13, 2025).
9. Wikipedia. Economy of Kazakhstan. Available at: <https://en.wikipedia.org> (last accessed: September 13, 2025).
10. Based on 2024 data from the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Available at: <https://stat.uz> (last accessed: September 10, 2025).

Additional Sources

1. Abduvaliev, M. (2024). An Overview of Central Asian Trade Growth and Economic Integration. CAREC Institute. Available at: <https://www.carecinstitute.org/publications/overview-central-asia-trade-2024>.
2. OECD. (2023). Trade Facilitation in Central Asia. OECD Publishing. Available at: <https://www.oecd.org/central-asia/trade-facilitation-2023.pdf>.
3. Yusupov, Yu. (2025). Foreign Trade of Central Asian Countries: Trends, Barriers, and Prospects. Available at: <https://www.centralasia-trade.org/foreign-trade-report-2025>.
4. World Trade Organization (WTO). Uzbekistan Profile. Available at: https://www.wto.org/english/thewto_e/countries_e/uzbekistan_e.htm.
5. Asian Development Bank (ADB). Central Asia Economic Update. Available at: <https://www.adb.org/countries/central-asia/main>.
6. OECD. Trade in Central Asia. Available at: <https://www.oecd.org/countries/central-asia/>.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 10

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>